

1 **Skill assessment of HF radar-derived products for lagrangian simulations in**
2 **the Bay of Biscay**

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ABSTRACT

17 Since January 2009, two long-range high-frequency (HF) radar systems
18 have been collecting hourly, high spatial resolution surface current data in
19 the south-eastern Bay of Biscay. The temporal resolution of the HF radar sur-
20 face currents permits to simulate drifter trajectories with the same time step
21 as that of real drifters deployed in the region in 2009. The main goal of this
22 work is to compare real drifter trajectories with trajectories computed from
23 HF radar currents obtained using different methods, including forecast cur-
24 rents. Open-Boundary Modal Analysis (OMA) is applied to the radar radial
25 velocities, and then a linear autoregressive model on the Empirical Orthogonal
26 Functions (EOF) decomposition of an historical data series is used to forecast
27 OMA currents. Additionally, the accuracy of the forecast method in terms of
28 spatial and temporal distribution of the lagrangian distances between observa-
29 tions and forecasts is investigated for a 4-year period (2009-2012). The skills
30 of the different HF radar products are evaluated within a 48-hour window.
31 Mean distances between real trajectories and their radar derived counterparts
32 range from 4 to 5 km for real-time and forecast currents, respectively, after 12
33 h of simulations. The forecast model improves persistence (i.e. the simula-
34 tions obtained by using the last available OMA fields as a constant variable)
35 after 6 h of simulation and improves the estimation of trajectories up to 28%
36 after 48 h. The performance of the forecast is observed to be variable in space
37 and time, related to the different ocean processes governing the local ocean
38 circulation.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Since January 2009, two long-range high-frequency (HF) radar systems have been collecting
41 hourly, high spatial resolution surface current data (~ 5 km) in the south-eastern Bay of Biscay.
42 The study area is situated between $1^\circ\text{W} - 3^\circ 30'\text{W}$ and $43^\circ 30'\text{N} - 44^\circ 40'\text{N}$ (Figure 1), off the
43 coast of the Basque Country, Spain, and south-western France. The coast is oriented roughly
44 east-west along the Spanish coast and north-south along the French coast, and this discontinuity
45 delineates the main bathymetric features of the study region. Figure 1 shows that the French
46 shelf becomes progressively wider to the north, while the Spanish shelf is much narrower with a
47 constant width (30-40 km) over the entire study area.

48
49 The primary circulation pattern in the SE Bay of Biscay is cyclonic in winter, with a reversal
50 to anticyclonic circulation in summer. The analysis of low-pass filtered currents shows that a
51 key component of this variability is associated with the surface signature of the slope current
52 (Iberian Poleward current, hereafter IPC) which is more intense over the upper part of the
53 slope (Solabarrieta et al. 2014). In winter, the IPC flows eastward along the Spanish coast and
54 northward along the French coast, affecting the upper water column from the surface to 300 m
55 depth (Le Cann and Serpette 2009) and associated with warm surface waters along the northern
56 Spanish slope (Pingree and Le Cann 1990). From the joint analysis of ADCP, HF radar, and
57 NAO index databases, eastward (northward) surface currents of 70 cm s^{-1} were observed along
58 the Spanish (French) slope, related to the winter IPC (Solabarrieta et al. 2014). In summer,
59 the circulation over the slope is reversed, i.e., presents a westward (southward) flow over the
60 Spanish (French) slope, with intensities three times weaker ($\sim 10\text{--}20 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) than those observed
61 in winter (Solabarrieta et al. 2014). Due to the stronger stratification of the water column, the

62 vertical gradients of the horizontal currents in summer show a higher vertical shear than in winter
63 (Rubio et al. 2013a).

64

65 In addition to the marked seasonality of the shelf/slope current regime, several authors have
66 described the presence of mesoscale cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies in the area. These eddies are
67 generated most frequently during winter by the interaction of the IPC with the abrupt bathymetry
68 (Pingree and Le Cann (1990); Pingree and Le Cann (1992a); Pingree and Le Cann (1992b); van
69 Aken and Hendrik (2002); Le Cann and Serpette (2009)). Recently, Rubio et al. (2013b) provided
70 evidence for the presence of coherent mesoscale structures within the HF radar footprint area and
71 on their potential effect on local transport paths.

72

73 Overlaid to the density-driven slope circulation, wind-induced currents are the main drivers
74 of the surface ocean circulation in the HF radar footprint area and are observed in a wide range
75 of time scales, from seasonal to high-frequency (Fontán et al. (2013); Fontán and Cornuelle
76 (2015); Solabarrieta et al. (2015); Kersalé et al. (2015)). During autumn and winter, SW winds
77 dominate and generate northward and eastward drift over the shelf. The wind regime changes
78 to the NE during spring, when it causes sea currents toward the W-SW along the Spanish coast.
79 The summer situation is similar to that of spring, but the weakness of the winds and the greater
80 variability of the direction of the general drift make currents more uncertain (González et al.
81 (2004); Solabarrieta et al. (2015)). Solabarrieta et al. (2015) used k-means clustering technique to
82 characterize the main ocean surface circulation patterns in the study area, at scales from several
83 days to interannual, showing the high variability in terms of surface currents and wind-current
84 interactions.

85

86 At shorter time-scales, the variability is dominated by inertial oscillations and tides (mainly
87 semidiurnal), although energy contents around the main tidal peaks are lower than in other
88 areas of the Bay (Le Cann 1990). Indeed, values observed for M2, which is the most energetic
89 component, are below 10 cm s^{-1} (Le Cann (1990); Rubio et al. (2013a)). The contribution of
90 inertial oscillations to the shear-induced vertical mixing over the slope was discussed by Rubio
91 et al. (2013a). From HF radar data, the distribution of kinetic energy around the inertial band
92 and its contribution to the total variability was observed to be highly variable in time and space;
93 inertial oscillations are seasonally modulated and intensified in summer in the central part of the
94 study area (Rubio et al. (2011); Solabarrieta et al. (2014)). Surface inertial currents over 15 cm
95 s^{-1} have been observed over the slope of the study area during stratified conditions (Rubio et al.
96 (2011)).

97
98 An area characterized by such complex circulation patterns and where relevant human activi-
99 ties linked to marine resources concentrate (artisanal and commercial fishing, tourism, industry,
100 increasing offshore aquaculture and marine renewables, etc.) represents a particular challenge for
101 the accurate monitoring and forecast of surface transport patterns. In this context, the main goal
102 of this paper is to compare real drifter trajectories with simulated trajectories computed from HF
103 radar-derived currents using different processing methodologies, including forecast currents. The
104 temporal resolution of the HF radar derived surface currents (hourly data) enables the simulation
105 of surface drifter trajectories with the same time step as that of real drifters that were deployed in
106 the region during several campaigns in 2009 (Charria et al. 2013). Additionally, the performances
107 of the forecast method used here are investigated, using a longer period of available HF radar data,
108 in terms of spatial and temporal distribution of lagrangian distances between radar-derived and
109 forecast trajectories.

110 **2. Data and methods**

111 *a. Data*

112 A main component of the Basque Country's in-situ Operational Oceanography observational
113 network is a 2 long range CODAR-Seasonde HF radar system, owned by the Directorate of
114 Emergency Attention and Meteorology of the Basque Government Security Department. The
115 radar antennas are located at Cape Matxitxako and Cape Higer (Figure 1) and emit at a central
116 frequency of 4.5 MHz and a 40 kHz bandwidth. The range coverage of radial data is close to 180
117 km, with 5 km radial resolution.

118
119 Hourly HF radar data within the period 2009-2012 are used in this study. Basque HF radar
120 validation exercises with suitable results have been done previously by several authors and they
121 can be checked in Solabarrieta et al. (2014) and Rubio et al. (2011). HF radar technology is more
122 detailed in Paduan and Rosenfeld (1996); Paduan and Graber (1997) and Paduan and Washburn
123 (2013).

124
125 From April to September 2009, different campaigns launched several drifter buoys within the
126 Bay of Biscay and 20 of them were used in this study. More information about the buoys can
127 be obtained in Charria et al. (2013). All the buoys had similar characteristics, with a surface oat
128 linked to a long (~ 10 m long \times ~ 1 m wide) holey sock drogue by a thin (~ 5 mm) cable and
129 centered at 15 m depth. The position was transferred by an ARGOS localization system every
130 hour. The lifetimes of the 20 real buoys used in this study ranged from several days to more than 3
131 months. The spatial distribution of the drifters is plotted in Figure 1 and the temporal distribution
132 these data within the period April to September 2009, and conditioned to the availability of HF

133 radar data can be checked in Solabarrieta et al. (2014) (Figure 2). The drifters covered distances
134 from few km up to 443 km, with speeds between 6.78-37.95 cm s⁻¹ (mean value of 18.69 cm s⁻¹
135 and standard deviation of 9.08cm s⁻¹). As the buoys were linked to a drogue centered at 15 m
136 depth, it is important to highlight that the deployments took place during mostly stratified months.
137 The same drifter data set was used for eulerian comparisons with HF radar velocities in Solabarri-
138 eta et al. (2014). The differences observed between drifter-derived velocities and HF radar within
139 the HF radar footprint area showed RMS values of approximately 13 cms-1. These values were
140 in agreement with those obtained though comparison with current data at 12 m measured by the
141 ADCPs located in two moored buoys over the slope during stratified conditions. The differences
142 observed between HF radar data and moored ADCP velocities in stratified conditions for a longer
143 time-series (2009-2011) were similar and higher than those observed in well-mixed periods. As al-
144 ready discussed in Solabarrieta et al. (2014), when analyzing the comparisons between the drifters
145 used here and the HF radar data, it has to be kept in mind that the effective averaging depth for sur-
146 face current measurements by HF radars has been estimated as 5%-16% of the wavelength of the
147 backscattering surface waves (Barrick (1977); Fernández et al. (1996); Stewart and Joy (1974)).
148 For the Basque Country system (4.5 MHz) the measurements made are expected to integrate cur-
149 rents vertically within the first ~2 m of the water column. Since the nominal depth of the available
150 drifter trajectories ranges from 10 to 20 m and most of the trajectories are obtained during stratified
151 conditions, part of the differences in the drift between real and simulated trajectories can be related
152 to the vertical shear of the current (detailed in Figure 5 in Solabarrieta et al. (2014)). Moreover,
153 it can also be expected that horizontal current shear also contribute to the differences observed
154 between measurements (drifters measure currents at punctual locations and discrete times while
155 HF radar velocities are running averages over 3 h and several square kilometers).

156 *b. Methods*

157 The received signal, an averaged Doppler backscatter spectrum received every 20 minutes, was
158 processed to radial current using the MUSIC (MUltiple Signal Classification) algorithm (Schmidt
159 1986) as applied by the manufacturer, CODAR Ocean Sensors, Ltd. The radial velocity fields
160 obtained were stored hourly after applying a running-average smoother (centered on a 3 hour win-
161 dow). For this work, the radial velocities were quality controlled and converted to total fields, using
162 the HFR_Progs MATLAB package (<https://cencalarchive.org/~cocmpmb/COCMPwiki/>),
163 based on Gurgel (1994) and Lipa and Barrick (1983) (see section 2.6). To obtain total currents
164 gridded into a 5 km resolution regular orthogonal mesh (see Figure 1), a least mean square
165 algorithm (spatial interpolation radius of 10 km) was applied. Both spatial resolution for the total
166 grid and the interpolation radius were chosen to resolve the smallest spatial scales within the
167 limits of the resolution of the radial data

168
169 Using the same grid, radial velocities are processed with HFR_Progs to generate Open Mode
170 Analysis (OMA) derived currents (Kaplan and Lekien 2007), hereafter OMA currents. OMA
171 analysis is a robust methodology that permits to generate gap-filled total currents from radials.
172 OMA analysis can also be used to produce total currents when the radial data coverage is not
173 complete or a radial file is missing, and also to increase the coverage in the baseline area. To
174 be able to make comparison between OMA and total currents, for our study we use OMA
175 currents only in the time steps where the two radial files exist and in the areas where the GDOP
176 (Geometrical Dilution of Precision) quality criteria errors are under established thresholds (see
177 Solabarrieta et al. (2014)). In this study, a total of 85 physical modes were used to build velocity

178 fields with a 20 km spatial resolution.

179

180 Finally, to forecast OMA interpolated currents, we used the linear autoregressive models
181 described in Frolov et al. (2012). In short, the Empirical Orthogonal Function (EOF) analysis was
182 first applied to the OMA gridded fields and the 50 leading EOF modes were retained. For the time
183 series of these leading EOF modes, a vector autoregressive model was constructed and then used
184 for prediction. Because of the combination of the EOF pre-processing and the time-embedding in
185 the autoregressive model (up to 48 h in the past), the forecast model is able to simultaneously learn
186 both the high-frequency signal (tidal and inertial) and the basin-wide modes of the circulation.

187

188 An example of the fields obtained, using the previously described processing methods for 13
189 February 2011 13:00, is provided in Figure 2. In this example, the radial coverage is not the opti-
190 mal for the system with reduced ranges for Higer antenna at bearing angles (i.e. the direction from
191 the radar site location to the radial grid point, bearing 90° means that radial grid point is located
192 north of the radar site location) between $80^\circ - 90^\circ$ and reduced ranges for Matxitxako antenna
193 from 0° to 30° . As a result total velocities at the SE corner of the footprint area cannot be obtained
194 using the least mean square algorithm (Figure 2; top, right). The OMA reconstruction is able to
195 fill this spatial gap and results in a current field very similar to the total field. The 24-h forecast
196 in Figure 2 (bottom, right) is calculated from the OMA field of 12 February 12 2011 13:00 using
197 the forecast model. In this example, the resulting field for 13 February shows similar structures to
198 the OMA field for the same date and time but weaker intensities, and spatially smoothed velocities.

199

200 To simulate trajectories in the differently processed HF radar current fields, a new version
201 (adapted to 2D fields) of the Lagrangian particle-tracking model (LPTM) developed by Ferrer

202 et al. (2009) for 3D numerical simulations of currents, was used here. The method for the particle
203 movement in this LPTM is based upon the 4th order RungeKutta scheme (Benson 1992) and
204 permits the calculation of multiple trajectories at a low computational cost. Trajectories obtained
205 using as a constant variable the latest available OMA current field at the time of simulations start
206 (hereafter persistence currents) are also included in the comparisons. This enables the estimation
207 of the variability of the current field during the simulation period and offers a reference for
208 evaluating the benefits of using forecast currents instead of persistence fields for operational
209 purposes.

210
211 For the comparison with the in-situ trajectories, and in order to have more than one comparison
212 trajectory for each real drifter track (20 real drifters in total), one trajectory was generated every 6
213 h starting along the corresponding positions of each real track, obtaining more than 4500 starting
214 points to simulate trajectories for comparison exercises. Each particle was then advected during 48
215 h using the LPTM and the currents of the differently processed data sets. In this way, the number
216 of comparison tracks increased substantially (see Figure 3, top and middle, as an example of the
217 comparison track obtained for one particle). For the analysis of the forecast model performances
218 in a longer period, trajectories have been generated every hour using trajectories launched in a
219 regular 9×7 grid, covering the study area with regular node distances of $0.15^\circ \times 0.09^\circ$ (Figure
220 3, bottom). In all cases, the trajectories of the particles going out of the HF radar footprint at
221 any time of the simulation are disregarded. As can be observed in this example, the trajectories
222 generated using persistence fields are quite similar to those generated using time-evolving OMA
223 currents, and suggesting the current pattern observed at the initial time step (Figure 2, bottom
224 left) persists during the following 48 h. In consequence the differences between persistence and
225 forecast are weak in most of the domain. The strongest differences are observed at the east part of

226 the domain where the trajectories obtained using the forecast show smaller differences with their
227 OMA counterparts. Persistence fields generate smooth trajectories which tend to overestimate the
228 net displacement of the particles in the OMA fields.

229

230 The differences between real and simulated trajectories have been estimated using the separa-
231 tion distance average ($\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$) between real and simulated trajectories. The mean separation
232 distances obtained using all the comparison pairs (real trajectories vs. simulated trajectories with
233 differently processed current fields) have been plotted against time up to 48 h (Figures 4 and 5).
234 The spatial distribution of longitude and latitude distances between real and simulated trajectories
235 has been also analyzed in order to detect any anisotropy in the differences between them.

236

237 Then, probability density distribution of distances between real and simulated trajectories after
238 6, 12, 24 and 48 h have been computed. To have a robust quantification of the main differences
239 between trajectories, a lognormal function has been adjusted to the distributions of distances.
240 Then, the lognormal probability density function can be obtained using:

241

$$y = f(x|\mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{x\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\ln x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

242 Where μ and σ are the mean the standard deviation, respectively, of the lognormal distribution
243 for the fitted data. The mean and standard deviation of each fit function, and the values of these
244 two parameters corresponding to the lower and upper confidence bounds within a 95% confidence
245 interval, are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2. Finally, the benefits of using forecast currents
246 instead of persistence currents are calculated as a dimensionless percent value using:

247

$$100 \times \frac{D_p - D_f}{D_p}$$

248 Where D_p is the mean distance obtained using persistence and D_f is the mean distance obtained
249 using the forecast model (Table 3).

250 **3. Comparison between HF radar-derived and real trajectories**

251 The average separation velocity (km h^{-1}) of the studied real drifters is 0.75 km h^{-1} . The
252 cumulative separation distances between the real and the simulated trajectories (Figure 4) show
253 separation rates (i.e. the increase with time of the mean distances between trajectories) of 0.5 km
254 h^{-1} between the real the simulated trajectories, along the first 6 h of simulation. No difference
255 in performance between the differently processed HF radar data are observed at shorter time lags
256 (Figure 4). After 6 h of simulation, differences start to be visible, with total and OMA currents
257 presenting the lowest separation ratio, of 0.27 and 0.37 km h^{-1} , respectively. The trajectories
258 obtained using forecast currents show a separation ratio similar to OMA trajectories (0.33 km
259 h^{-1}) while the trajectories obtained assuming persistence of the initial OMA field show higher
260 errors (with a separation ratio of 0.4 km h^{-1}). At the end of the simulation (48 h) the trajectories
261 obtained using OMA and forecast currents present separation distances over 10 km with respect
262 to the real ones, while those obtained using persistence currents show separation distances over
263 15 km.

264

265 The values obtained by adjusting a lognormal curve to the probability density distributions of
266 the distances between all the trajectories at 6, 12, 24 and 48 h are shown in Table 1. After 6 h,
267 the separation distance from real drifters is around 2.85 km for totals and 2.98 km for forecast
268 currents, while these values increase up to 6.59 and 7.93 km, respectively, after 24 h of simulation.

269 The separation distances obtained using OMA currents are between these values. This means that
270 the inaccuracies in the OMA solution for total currents are contributing to the differences observed
271 using the forecast model and the persistence fields, both obtained using OMA currents. Persistence
272 shows separation values with respect to real trajectories over 10 km after 24 h of simulation. The
273 examination of the zonal and meridional distances with time does not show any anisotropy (not
274 shown).

275 **4. Analysis of the forecast model spatio-temporal performances**

276 The cumulative separation distances between simulated trajectories using OMA and those
277 obtained using persistence and forecast currents are examined for two different seasons in the
278 period 2009-2012 (Figure 5). The separation between the simulated trajectories using OMA and
279 the ones using forecast and persistence currents are similar during the first 6 h of simulation
280 (around 0.44 km h^{-1}). The separation rates vary seasonally from 0.54 km h^{-1} in summer to 0.3
281 km h^{-1} in winter. In both cases, and both data sets, the separation rates for time horizons of 24-48
282 h are lower: around 0.41 km h^{-1} and 0.33 km h^{-1} for persistence and forecast, respectively,
283 in summer and 0.24 km h^{-1} and 0.22 km h^{-1} for persistence and forecast, respectively, in
284 winter. A higher rate of separation between persistence and OMA trajectories indicates higher
285 spatial-temporal variability in summer currents, despite the fact that they are expected to be
286 much less intense than the wintertime currents. Similarly, a higher rate of separation between
287 persistence and forecast trajectories suggests that the skills of the forecast model to predict
288 summer much more variable current fields are lower. It is worth noting that the skills of
289 the forecast model in summer are lower to those shown by persistence trajectories in winter.
290 However, Figure 4 suggests that the benefits of the forecast relative to persistence currents are
291 higher in summer than in winter. At the end of the simulation (48 h) the trajectories obtained

292 using forecast currents present distances around 7.5 and 10 km in winter and summer, respectively.

293

294 The values obtained by adjusting a lognormal curve to the probability density distributions
295 of the distances between all the simulated trajectories for the different seasons at 6, 12, 24
296 and 48 h are shown in Table 2. After 6 h, the mean separation distance for forecast currents
297 is around 3.29 and 1.8 km in summer and winter, respectively while these values after 24 h of
298 simulation increase until 7.95 and 5.33 km, in summer and winter, respectively. Persistence
299 shows separation values with respect to OMA trajectories of 10 km in summer and 5.8 km in
300 winter after 24 h of simulation. As for the comparison with real trajectories no anisotropy was
301 found in the distributions of the zonal and meridional distances at any simulation time (not shown).

302

303 When the results are analyzed spatially significant differences in the performance of the forecast
304 model can also be observed, which are in agreement with the spatial variability of the persistence.
305 In summer (Figure 6), the area where trajectories are reproduced with the lowest skills is the NW
306 of the domain, being the distances lower in the south of the domain and along the shelf and slope.
307 Differences between OMA trajectories and those in persistence and forecast are the highest and
308 can reach values at the NW part of the domain, over 12 and 20 km, at 24 and 48 h, respectively. In
309 summer differences between trajectories using OMA currents and persistence are high (>20 km)
310 in almost all the domain after 48 h, while these are still under 12 km over the slope area for the
311 forecast currents (Figure 6). The benefits of forecast in summer can be seen mostly in this area of
312 low persistence.

313

314 In winter (Figure 7), an area with increased differences between OMA and persistence and fore-
315 casts located at the NW of the domain can be still observed but it is much more reduced spatially.

316 High differences between trajectories are instead observed along the shelf/slope. Globally, abso-
317 lute differences are lower in winter than in summer in the whole domain. Values at the slope area
318 over 6.5 km and 12.7 km can be observed for persistence at 24 and 48 h, respectively (Figure 7).
319 These are reduced by the forecast to values over 5.5 km and 10 km at 24 h and 48 h, respectively.

320 **5. Discussion**

321 The skills of different HF radar-derived products to reproduce observed trajectories have been
322 analyzed using real drifter data available within the radar footprint area in 2009. Further analyses
323 have been performed using the complete HF radar data set available for the study area in order to
324 investigate the temporal and spatial variability of the performances of the forecast products.

325
326 The differences between real trajectories and simulated trajectories obtained using HF radar
327 total currents show values between 2.85 km and 6.59 km after 6 h and 24 h of simulation,
328 respectively. Similarly to what was discussed in Solabarrieta et al. (2014) and Rubio et al. (2011)
329 in terms of Eulerian differences, different aspects can contribute to the differences between the
330 real and HF radar-derived trajectories obtained here. Since vertical and horizontal current shears
331 can be expected to have been high in the period when the drifters were deployed, it can be
332 expected that the skills of the HF radar-derived total velocities to reproduce real trajectories will
333 be improved for periods with greater homogeneity in the upper part of the water column. These
334 differences can also be expected to be reduced by the use of surface drifters (e.g. CODE drifters,
335 see Berta et al. (2014)), with equivalent integration depth to that of the Basque Country HF radar
336 system ($\sim 1\text{m}$), or by the use of drifter spatial clusters, as discussed in Ohlmann et al. (2007).

337

338 The quality of OMA reconstruction has also been proved by our results, since in the area
339 covered by two radials where total velocities reconstruction is possible, this solution does
340 significantly degrade the estimations. Higher inaccuracies due to the reconstruction from radials
341 to totals can be expected near the baseline area and also in periods of short temporal (few hours)
342 radial data gaps when OMA can still be used to retrieve total currents. The use of OMA velocities
343 when only one antenna is working and the analysis of the results using these velocities are out of
344 the scope of this paper. Although this possibility offers velocity fields with fewer gaps, which is
345 beneficial for operational use, it is also expected to add to the uncertainties.

346

347 In terms of forecast currents, the comparisons between projected and real trajectories lead
348 to mean differences under 3 km at 6 h (i.e., adding significant error to the estimation provided
349 by total currents) and under 8 km within a forecast horizon of 24 h. During all the simulation
350 periods, the forecasted trajectories represent improvements over the estimations provided by
351 persistence fields (i.e., considering the last available OMA field remains stationary for all the
352 simulation period). The comparison results are similar and agree with those obtained by Ullman
353 et al. (2006) and Kohut et al. (2012), using HF radar data and drifters. The benefit of the forecast
354 method with respect to persistence is of 12.5% after 12 h of simulations, and grows up to 28.6%
355 after 48 h (Table 3). These results are similar to the benefits of forecast trajectories relative to
356 persistence-based trajectories obtained using all available HF radar observations from 2009 to
357 2012, which show benefits around 15.0% after 12 h and 28.4% after 48 h.

358

359 When analyzing projected trajectories based on the forecast model and persistence for the
360 period 2009-2012, spatial and seasonal variability of the performances are observed. Seasonally,
361 the benefits of forecast relative to persistence range from 4% to 13.6% after 12 h and from 19.9%

362 to 27.26% after 48 h, with the highest benefits observed during the summer (Table 3). Indeed, in
363 summer, the errors of the forecast are higher in absolute values but since the surface current fields
364 are more variable (less persistent) the relative benefits of employing the forecast model are higher.
365 If we compute the average distances covered by the drifters simulated with OMA fields (that is
366 the separation with time along each trajectory from its starting positions), a dispersion rate of 0.2
367 km h^{-1} is observed in summer. By comparison, the separation rate between OMA trajectories
368 and forecast trajectories is around 0.33 km h^{-1} . Hence, we conclude that the skill of the forecast
369 product in summer needs to be improved. The winter situation is slightly different. Since there is
370 a more persistent current regime, the estimation of projected trajectories can, in general, be done
371 with lower errors. At the same time, the benefits of using forecast currents instead of persistence
372 are also lower. The average distance covered by winter drifters in time gives a dispersion rate
373 of 0.36 km h^{-1} , while forecasts provide trajectories with a mean separation rate from OMA
374 trajectories of 0.22 km h^{-1} .

375

376 When looking to the spatial distribution of inaccuracies in the forecast of trajectories, a good
377 correspondence between the region of highest forecast errors and those of less persistence can be
378 observed. This has a straightforward interpretation: the method is learning more easily the most
379 predictable patterns. What is interesting is that, in our study area, these regions are well defined
380 and clear relationships can be established with the dynamical features identified in previous
381 works, particularly those using HF radar data (e.g. Solabarrieta et al. (2014)). The best skills
382 are observed during winter when persistence of current patterns is higher. Spatially, during
383 winter the highest forecast errors are concentrated in the most energetic area where the seasonal
384 (and poleward) current is well established (Solabarrieta et al. 2014). During summer, when the
385 current regime is much more variable (mostly linked to more variable winds and a less intense

386 and persistent slope equatorward current), persistence and forecast fields present much lower
387 skills compared to the OMA fields. In both cases these are the lowest in the NW area where the
388 contribution of high-frequency (mostly inertial motions) processes can grow up to 40% of the total
389 kinetic energy (see Figure 8 of Solabarrieta et al. (2014)). These results point to a possible way to
390 improve forecast by improving the learning strategy of the model. Instead of using a multiyear
391 period of historical data, better results could be obtained by using seasonally conditioned learning
392 periods or by separating the different contributions of the different physical processes (which have
393 both different spatial and temporal variability scales) to the total variability before applying EOF
394 decomposition (and thus forcing EOFs to split correctly different physical signals). Also, the use
395 of HF radar data in combination with other datasets like current fields derived from ocean forecast
396 systems and forecast wind fields could help to improve forecast skills in the short term (after 12
397 hours of simulation). The benefits of using wind fields are discussed in Frolov et al. (2012).

398
399 Better results could also be expected for a higher resolution data set. The benefits of a long
400 range HF radar system reside in extended footprints but the resolution in space is reduced. For
401 some operational needs (i.e. Search and Rescue operations) higher resolution fields could be
402 more appropriate. New analyses using the data closer to the antennas, where refined grids for
403 total velocities can be obtained due to a denser coverage of radials, are needed to evaluate further
404 the possibility of improved forecasts. In any case it has to be highlighted that for all the analyses
405 performed, the forecast method is always equal to or better than the persistence fields and very
406 similar to those of the total fields. This result confirms the utility of the forecast method for both
407 short time lags and for wide forecast windows up to 48 h for which the observed errors are under
408 15 km.

409

410 The results obtained in our experiments prove the adequacy of the HF radar used here to provide
411 data for operational monitoring of the coastal areas. Indeed, the use of real-time HF radar data
412 and derived products, such as the short-term forecast, has proven to have significant impact on
413 the reduction of operational search radii in real situations (e.g. Roarty et al. (2010), Breivik et al.
414 (2012)). Other examples of the application of these data to different issues have been detailed
415 in several publications (Paduan and Washburn (2013); Wyatt (2014)). It is worth noting that
416 the computational requirements to obtain forecast velocity fields are similar to those to compute
417 OMA velocity fields, so they could be generated operationally.

418
419 Finally, the high correlation observed between HF radar-derived surface currents and those along
420 the water column shown in Solabarrieta et al. (2014) opens new research lines towards the estima-
421 tion and forecast of 4D ocean transports using operational HF radar data in combination with other
422 observations to provide information about the dynamics at deeper levels. The vertical coherence
423 for surface patterns is expected to be seasonally modulated. Thus, again, careful choices of the
424 data periods and analysis strategy should be made in view of the physical processes characterizing
425 the local dynamics.

426 **6. Conclusion**

427 The skills to reproduce observed trajectories of real-time and forecast HF radar-derived prod-
428 ucts have been analyzed using a set of drifter data available in the radar footprint area in 2009.
429 Then, the skills of the short term forecast model (Frolov et al. 2012) used to obtain forecast from
430 hourly current fields are analyzed in terms of spatial and temporal distributions, for a longer time
431 period. This paper provides quantitative evaluation of the capability of a coastal long-range HF
432 radar data system to generate trajectories for real situations, with reasonable accuracy and low

433 computational costs. Besides, the forecast model used here is proved to provide accurate forecast
434 of real trajectories within operational window of 48 h. The benefits of the forecast methodology
435 in absolute terms and with respect to the persistence fields are shown to be variable in time and
436 space in relation to the modulation of the different physical processes governing the local ocean
437 circulation. New approaches for improved forecasts are suggested in light of the obtained results
438 and deserve further research.

439 *Acknowledgments.* The work of L. Solabarrieta in this study has been supported by the PhD grant
440 of Fundación Centros Tecnológicos Iaki Goenaga. The work of A. Rubio and J. Mader has been
441 partially supported by JERICO_NEXT project, funded by the European Commission's H2020 Pro-
442 gramme (Contract 65 4410). Authors thank the Directorate of Emergency Attention and Meteoro-
443 logic of the Basque Government for providing the radial HF radar data. The HF radar-processing
444 toolbox HFR_Progs was provided by D. Kaplan, M. Cook, D. Atwater, and J. F. González. Finally,
445 we also thank the sampling staff of the Marine Research Division of AZTI-Tecnalia. This paper is
446 contribution no. 772 from AZTI-Marine Research.

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561 brackets. 27

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564 months in the period 2009-2012, using OMA derived trajectories) and Winter
565 (for winter months in the period 2009-2012, using OMA derived trajectories).
566 Benefit in percent is calculated as detailed in section 1.2. 28

567 TABLE 1. Statistical parameters for lognormal distributions of distances between real and simulated trajec-
568 tories in figure 5, after 6, 12, 24 and 48 h of simulations with total, OMA, persistence and forecast currents.
569 SD: Stantard Deviation. Values correpondig to the distributions within the 95th percentile are given in square
570 brackets.

<i>Time(h)</i>	<i>Totals</i>		<i>OMA</i>		<i>Persistence</i>		<i>Forecast</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
6	2.85	2.01	2.91	2.14	3.15	2.51	2.98	2.24
	[2.61, 3.14]	[1.69, 2.42]	[2.65, 3.21]	[1.081, 2.58]	[2.85, 3.49]	[2.09, 3.05]	[2.69, 3.34]	[1.85, 2.77]
12	4.07	3.19	4.47	3.61	6.05	5.08	5.29	4.12
	[3.68, 4.54]	[2.65, 3.91]	[4.01, 4.96]	[2.99, 4.43]	[5.44, 6.77]	[4.20, 6.24]	[4.74, 5.95]	[3.37, 5.14]
24	6.59	5.25	7.42	6.13	10.23	9.47	7.93	6.36
	[5.92, 7.38]	[4.32, 6.49]	[6.66,8.33]	[5.03, 7.59]	[9.08, 11.64]	[7.68, 11.93]	[7.06,9.00]	[5.13,8.05]
48	10.29	7.51	12.16	11.16	17.65	14.74	12.59	10.87
	[9.28,11.51]	[6.17, 9.31]	[10.68,14.01]	[8.88, 14.37]	[15.7, 20.04]	[11.92, 18.62]	[10.98,14.65]	[8.50, 14.31]

571 TABLE 2. Statistical parameters for lognormal distributions of distances between (a) OMA and persistence
572 trajectories and between (b) OMA and forecast trajectories, after 6, 12, 24 and 48 h of simulation. SD: Standard
573 Deviation. Values corresponding to the distributions within the 95th percentile are given in square brackets.

		<i>(a) Persistence</i>		<i>(b) Forecast</i>	
	<i>Time(h)</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
all period	6	2.68	2.27	2.69	2.21
		[2.67,2.7]	[2.25,2.29]	[2.68,2.71]	[2.19,2.23]
	12	5.29	4.62	4.54	3.84
		[5.26,5.32]	[4.58,4.67]	[4.51,4.57]	[3.8,3.88]
24	8.68	7.32	6.87	5.54	
	[8.63,8.73]	[7.25,7.4]	[6.83,6.91]	[5.49,5.6]	
48	16.2	13.55	11.62	9.35	
	[16.11, 16.29]	[13.42, 13.69]	[11.56,11.68]	[9.26, 9.44]	
Summer	6	3.25	2.55	3.29	2.59
		[3.21,3.28]	[2.5,2.6]	[3.25,3.32]	[2.54,2.63]
	12	6.27	4.86	5.42	4.29
		[6.2,6.33]	[4.77,4.95]	[5.37,5.48]	[4.21,4.37]
24	10.05	7.88	7.95	5.94	
	[9.95,10.16]	[7.74,8.03]	[7.88,8.03]	[5.84,6.05]	
48	18.36	13.83	13.37	10.14	
	[18.18, 18.54]	[13.59, 14.09]	[13.24, 13.5]	[9.96, 10.33]	
Winter	6	1.69	1.38	1.8	1.41
		[1.67,1.71]	[1.35,1.41]	[1.78,1.82]	[1.38,1.44]
	12	3.21	2.55	3.08	2.56
		[3.18,3.25]	[2.49,2.6]	[3.04,3.12]	[2.51,2.62]
24	5.8	4.6	5.33	4.42	
	[5.73,5.87]	[4.5,4.7]	[5.27,5.4]	[4.32,4.52]	
48	11.25	9.28	9.01	7.78	
	[11.11, 11.39]	[9.08, 9.49]	[8.89, 9.12]	[7.61, 7.96]	

574 TABLE 3. Benefit of STP compared to persistence for 6,12,24 and 48 h time lags in the different study
 575 periods: 2009 (using real trajectories), Summer (for summer months in the period 2009-2012, using OMA
 576 derived trajectories) and Winter (for winter months in the period 2009-2012, using OMA derived trajectories).
 577 Benefit in percent is calculated as detailed in section 1.2.

<i>Time(h)</i>	2009	2009 – 2012	<i>Summer</i>	<i>Winter</i>
12	12.5%	15.1%	13.6%	4%
24	22.5%	20.9%	20.9%	8%
48	28.6%	28.4%	27.2%	19.9%

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580 capes. Grey points correspond to the nodes of the grid used to build radar-derived total
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620 FIG. 5. Time evolution of the mean separation distance between trajectories (solid lines) generated using
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